

APPLICATION OF THE HOLOGRAPHIC NONDESTRUCTIVE TESTING METHOD FOR EVALUATION OF DISBONDINGS IN SANDWICH PLATES

*Prof. Dr.-Ing., Dr. ir.h.c. Friedrich Erdmann-Jesnitzer
und Dipl.-Ing. Thees Winkler, Hannover (West Germany)*

Disbondings between core and facesheets of sandwich structures causing severe reductions in load bearing capacity make adequate controls necessary for security and reliability reasons. Beside other nondestructive testing methods quality control may take use of the holographic interferometry by the aid of which even smallest subsurface anomalies in sandwich panels can be made visible under some suitable way of stressing, clearly showing them as local irregularities in a fundamental fringe pattern. Stressing and deformation of sandwich test specimen by application of outside partial vacuum have given good results in fault detection, even when the vacuum was applied prior to -not during- the holographic measuring procedure. By using this holographic method also for testing industrially manufactured sandwich panels -consisting of rigid synthetic foam cores and skins of either glass fibre reinforced plastics or steel sheets- its high accuracy for detecting even small disbands, found in the laboratory stage of evaluation, could be verified. The results obtained offer some interesting aspects for future application in quality control and in-service testing of sandwich materials, though the commercial point of view has not enough been taken into consideration until now.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays also the building industry to an increasing extent makes use of multi-layer compound materials, so-called sandwich structures, for load bearing parts, i.e. roofs, walls and claddings. These materials are combining in an optimal manner extraordinary insulation properties, low structural weight and high bending stability. The bearing characteristics of these structures consisting of two facesheets (metals, plastics, wood, asbestoscement) and a core (honeycombs of metal, plastics or paper, balsa-wood or rigid foam) are based on the high mechanical strength of their strong but thin facesheets under normal stresses. The facesheets being supported by the extremely light core are kept in their position which is characterized by a large distance of the facesheets from each other in relation to their low thickness. The core itself is only suffering shear stresses in a small amount.

Though calculation methods for theoretical evaluation of rupture and deformation behaviour of these sandwich structures are available negative experiences in practical application show that often failure occurs prior to calculated values of load bearing capacity. This is beside others due to adhesive faults in the core-to-facesheet bond which means incomplete stress transfer between the different layers of the compound structure. Under compression stresses as well as increasing temperatures by solar radiation for example, these disbondings may initiate pre-buckling of the facesheets which might gradually increase in their dimensions and finally lead to a complete separation of large areas, thus producing failure.

For security reasons it is necessary in load bearing sandwich elements especially to detect possible disbondings - not only in the manufacturing stage but also in constructions already in service. Among other nondestructive testing methods the holographic interferometry, which has already gained some importance in testing aircraft and aerospace structures, offers good practicability for controlling complete sandwich components. One condition for successfully applying this method is a proper form of stressing the sandwich specimen to be tested in order to induce a noticeable deformation, i.e. differential bulging of the disbonded area. This is the only way to make the fault visible and apt to analysis under the testing conditions described in the following chapter.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR HOLOGRAPHIC INTERFEROMETRY

The holographic interferometry is a relatively new method for measuring displacements respectively deformations in the size of some lengths of light waves i.e. of some micrometers. As opposed to other optical measuring methods the holographic interferometry bases on the use of coherent light (laser) and thus could only be developed in recent years, since lasers of high output have been available, and from then on could find application in practical use.

Several reports on the principles of this measuring method as well as on its application in nondestructive testing of materials have already been issued. In a prior publication detail information on this subject is to be found, including the most important sources [1]. In the report presented hereby the physical basis will only be discussed to a degree necessary for the interpretation of the photographs (interferogrammes, fringe patterns) demonstrating measuring results and for explaining details in the experimental setup respectively procedure.

For this reason the principles of holographic interferometry may briefly be explained as follows:

The image (interferogramme) of the test specimen, making visible its deformation being caused by some kind of stressing, is produced by illuminating the specimen with laser light and by superimposing the reflected light beams in two different states of deformation to another mutually coherent light beam, the so-called

reference beam. All visual information about the illuminated surface of the object is stored as a so-called hologramme in a high resolution emulsion on a photographic plate, including phase as well as intensity (amplitude) of the wavefront reflected from it during exposure. Proper coherent illumination of the developed hologramme, with the reference beam for example, causes reconstruction of the object wavefront so that the observer can see a virtual image of the object, exactly like the actual object in size and apparent position. The photograph of this virtual image taken by focusing now through the optical plate is the basis for holographic evaluation, which means an image of the specimen covered with a fringe pattern corresponding to the local deformation between two different states of the sample as to be seen in some of the following figures.

The deformation patterns shown in these figures are produced applying outside partial vacuum to either one or both surfaces of the sandwich specimen to be tested. Thus a possible core-to-facesheet disbonding area is lifted from the core bending rectangular to the sandwich surface. The value of bending deformation depends on the dimensions of the disbonding, on the thickness and the modulus of elasticity (Young's modulus) of the facesheet and on the degree of partial vacuum.

The experimental setup for holographic evaluation of sandwich specimen stressed by partial vacuum mainly consists of optical components, i.e. lenses, mirrors, spatial filters and beam splitters. By these components the holographic beam is split up into an object and a reference partial beam, which are superimposed in the photographic emulsion after the object beam has been reflected by the specimen. At both surfaces of the sandwich specimen vacuum chambers are positioned exactly opposite to each other and sealed. The holographic setup used being extremely sensitive to vibrations was completely installed on a heavy vibration isolated concrete table, including the vacuum chambers, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Holographic setup for evaluation of disbondings in sandwich plates by applying partial outer vacuum for specimen deformation
 S = shutter, T = telescope, M = mirror, L = lens,
 SF = spatial filter, BS = beam splitter, H = holographic plate

The holographic fringe patterns shown later on were obtained in short-time experiments actually referred to under outside partial vacuum in such a manner that at first a pre-vacuum of approximately 0,7 bar was applied and the holographic plate was illuminated by the image of the specimen at this stage of deformation. The second illumination necessary for double-exposure technique was made after applying a differential vacuum varying between 0,005 and 0,05 bar, depending on the stiffness of the sandwich. The fringe pattern resulting thereof is holographically observed through a window (pressure resistant glass plate) in the vacuum chamber.

In holographic long-time experiments referred to later on, the necessary deformation differences were not produced elastically by a slight increase in stress but by temporal viscoelastic relaxation which occurs for example after a long-time "creep" producing partial vacuum and subsequent discharge. In those experiments the specimen were stressed over a certain period of time at approximately 0,7 bar in a vacuum unit installed separately from the holographic setup. After removal from the vacuum unit and resulting spontaneous elastic part of re-bending the specimen is positioned in the holographic setup in an object holder, Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Holographic setup installed on heavy vibration isolated table with specimen holder for "creep" experiments on square plates (left corner)

The two holographic exposures necessary for an interferometric image thereby were obtained during the subsequent temporal course of relaxation and re-bending. According to the type of the sandwich the exposures are made after different periods of relaxation time and with varying time differences between them. In these "creep" and relaxation experiments there was no glass plate in the optical path from the laser to the holographic plate via the reflecting surface of the specimen.

In holographic interferometry the fringe pattern results from superposition of the different states of deformation in the surface whereby the corresponding wavefronts locally intensify or extinguish each other due to face-shifting, i.e. they interfere.

In the optical setup this report is based on the resulting fringes resemble a topographic map of a hill, whereby the distance between two fringes correspond to half a wavelength of the laser light used. In quantitative analysis the vertical displacement d_{\perp} of any point in the illuminated area can be calculated according to Eq. (1).

$$d_{\perp} \text{ [}\mu\text{m]} = n \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} \approx n \cdot 0,3 \quad (1)$$

n = fringe order resp. number

λ = wavelength (632,8 nm for helium-neon laser)

Quantitative analysis suffers from errors in calculation of approx. 5 % due to dimensions of the illuminated area on the specimen surface as well as to the influence of the glass plate transmitted by the object beam and the sealing of the glass plate to the vacuum chamber.

SHORT-TIME EXPERIMENTS ON SANDWICH SPECIMEN
PRODUCED IN THE LABORATORY

In this stage of evaluation the sandwich specimen consisted of a rigid polyurethane foam core (density 50 kgs / m³, thickness 40 mm) covered on both sides with facesheets made of GRP, glassfibre reinforced polyester (glass contents approx. 30 weight-percent, thickness 1 to 8 mm). In most specimen circular disbondings from 10 to 50 mm in diameter were intentionally located between one skin and core, Fig.3.

Fig. 3 Double-exposure interferogrammes of sandwich plates with different faults made visible by stressing the plates by outer partial vacuum at the surfaces.
left: correct bonding, programmed disbond of 50 mm in diameter
right: faulty bonding, programmed disbond of 10 mm in diameter

The fringe patterns obtained with these specimen show certain characteristics, varying whether the outer vacuum is applied from one or from both sides, Fig. 4 and 5.

Under one-side-vacuum at the front skin only there occurs a total bending of the specimen freely supported by the edge of the vacuum chamber resembling a parabola. At the disbonded skin area a locally limited bulging can be seen in addition. This buckling is clearly visible and in cross-section also resembling a parabola when occurring under a thin facesheet, on the other hand it is hardly visible when under a thick facesheet.

Under bilateral vacuum there is no total bending of the plate to one side but an increase in thickness like a plateau and once more additionally the distinct parabola-like buckling in the disbond area, Fig. 4.

As a result it can be noticed that bilateral vacuum stressing produces interferogrammes with fundamental patterns of lower fringe number and with better possibilities for contouring disbonded areas. Only thus determination of dimensions as well as localisation of disbondings can be taken by evaluation of photographs or plotted curves, Fig. 5. Under bilateral vacuum stressing limits of detecting accuracy were found at disbondings down to a size of 50 mm in diameter under a 8 mm GRP skin resp. down to 10 mm in diameter under 1 mm GRP skin on a rigid polyurethane foam core.

Fig. 4 Double-exposure interferogrammes of a sandwich plate with programmed circular disbondings under partial vacuum on one surface (left) resp. both (right). Sandwich plate with 1 mm GRP skin, diameter of disbonding 50 mm, initial vacuum $p_1=0,5$ bar, differential vacuum $\Delta p=0,005$ bar

Fig. 5 Double-exposure fringe patterns and plotted bending curves of a sandwich plate under partial vacuum on one surface (a) resp. both surfaces (b). Sandwich plate with 3 mm GRP skins, disbonding diameter 50 mm $p_1 = 0,7$ bar, $\Delta p = 0,01$ bar

LONG-TIME EXPERIMENTS ON LABORATORY SANDWICH SPECIMEN

In the following "creep" experiments on sandwich specimen relaxation phenomena were used for holographic analysis by the double-exposure method, as a comparison between two different stages of deformation resp. time. "Creeping" occurs in all viscoelastic, i.e. synthetic materials under long-time static load.

After subsequent discharge the total deformation spontaneously decreases only by the elastic part of deformation, further on the viscoelastic part of deformation slowly decreases by relaxation. This course of relaxation going on the difference between two temporal stages of deformation is holographically measured, Fig. 6. For a procedure according to Fig. 6 the sandwich specimen were removed from the separate vacuum unit after long-time vacuum stressing and positioned in the holographic setup in a holder, only slightly fixed at the edges, Fig. 2.

Fig. 6 Schematical deflection curve of "creeping" materials in relation to loading stage and time (here: bending deformation of plates under one side partial vacuum)
 t_1 = loading time, t_u = uncharging time,
 t_x = relaxation time at the beginning of holographic procedure

The fringe patterns of these "creep" specimen show no remarkable differences as compared with the short-time patterns, except obvious additional fringes in the marginal areas of the specimen no longer being covered by the frame of the vacuum chamber, Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Double-exposure fringe patterns of a sandwich plate with programmed disbonding during relaxation after long-time bilateral stressing with outer partial vacuums
 left:
 relaxation time $t_1 = 2$ minutes, time difference $\Delta t_1 = 1$ minute
 right:
 relaxation time $t_2 =$ hours, time difference $\Delta t_2 = 2$ hours

Quantitative analysis of the interferogrammes as well as comparative measurements of skin strains using dial gauges showed an excellent detection and localisation accuracy for adhesive faults, even under minimal membrane stresses. These long-time experiments have furthermore proved no negative influence on the detecting accuracy by local and temporal separation of stressing procedure and holographic analysis. This works under the condition that the materials to be tested show sufficient "creep" under normal surrounding conditions.

The positive results holographically obtained in long-time experiments can be seen as a basis for further successfully examining larger sandwich elements with the intention of gaining total separation of heavy vacuum units from sensitive holographic setups.

LONG-TIME EXPERIMENTS ON INDUSTRIALLY MANUFACTURED
SANDWICH PLATES

Further creep experiments were carried out on specimen of larger dimensions (700 x 700 mm²) taken from different manufacturers and varying in materials combination. Cores were exclusively made of synthetic rigid foams, for example basing on polystyrene, polyvinylchloride, polyester, polyurethane and phenolic resin. Skins of glass-fibre-reinforced polyester, steel and aluminum were laminated, bonded or connected by foamed-in-place technique to the core.

In order to demonstrate normal holographic fringe patterns in the larger and square measuring area of the advanced type of vacuum and holographic equipment some basic photographs were made of bilateral stressed plates during relaxation, Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Normal fringe pattern of a sandwich plate without local faults after bilateral vacuum stressing.
Sandwich consisting of 60 mm rigid polyurethane foam core and 0,6 mm steel sheet
(black line vacuum chamber edges)

Circular disbands of known size and location intentionally located in different plates could be detected under a 4 mm GRP skin down to 30 mm in diameter. They could, however, be localized but hardly measured under a 1 mm steel sheet, Fig. 9.

These results verify the influence of "creep" properties of the compound resp. skin materials on the detecting accuracy of this testing method. Further sources of influence on the measuring contents of the fringe patterns obtained, i.e. deformations of the whole plate, optical and mechanical details of the setup, holographic experimental parameters and so on, have already been discussed in another report [2] .

Fig. 9 Fringe patterns of industrially manufactured sandwich plates with programmed disbondings of varying diameter after bilateral vacuum stressing.
 left: sandwich with 4 mm GRP on PUR core
 right: sandwich with 0,6 mm steel on PUR core

In the following it shall only be demonstrated by some examples and recent results which types of disbonds in industrially manufactured sandwich plates due to faulty production can be made visible in holographic fringe patterns.

A sandwich plate consisting of brittle rigid polyester foam filled with ground minerals and covered with GRP skins of 3 mm thickness showed during relaxation a holographic fundamental fringe pattern of only low fringe number. A small almost circular disbond due to accumulated filler was clearly detectable. Another plate of the same type showed two small disbonds as well as some irregularities in the fringe pattern due to inhomogeneous bonding in greater parts of the measuring area, Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Fringe patterns of specimen from industrially manufactured plates with production faults, i.e. circular disbondings (left) and additional inhomogeneous bonding in parts of the plate (right). Sandwich consisting of 85 mm rigid polyester foam, filled with ground minerals, and 3 mm GRP facesheets.

One plate made of the same rigid foam, filled with expanded silicate, gave similar results. In this case the fault was caused by a broken particle of expanded silicate of approx. 15 mm in diameter, located directly under the skin, Fig. 11. Due to the high rigidity of the core and the stiffness of the skin material the disbonded areas only bulge up to one fringe order, which means approx. 0,3 μ m from the surface, but they are clearly detectable.

Fig. 11 Fringe patterns of industrial specimen with local circular disbonding (left) resp. without (right) but unusually curved fringes fundamental due to shifting and torsion of the plate during relaxation and holographic procedure. Sandwich consisting of 90 mm rigid polyester foam, filled with expanded silicate, and 3 mm GRP facesheets.

The proof of detecting these local irregularities of minimal size gives an impression of the measuring accuracy of this method, also suitable for entire-surface evaluation of large measuring areas.

For a further application of holographic interferometry as a nondestructive testing method for production quality control as well as in-service-checking the separation between stressing procedure and holographic analysis realised with "creeping" materials could be an important step. The use of simple and non-expensive holographic equipment could be made possible. On the other hand the advantage of gaining interference patterns of high accuracy is combined with the disadvantage of the time-consuming and laborious vacuum stressing process.

Another method which might be less complicated, faster and demanding less energy could be the application of heat to the surfaces to induce the necessary deformations.

Research results of other authors available up to now as well as own experiences from first experiments using this method of thermal stressing suffer from a certain inaccuracy as opposed to the results by vacuum stressing discussed in this report, Fig. 12 and 13.

Fig. 12 Fringe pattern of a sandwich plate (similar to that in Fig. 7) during thermal relaxation after stressing by slight temperature increase at one side.

Fig. 13 Fringe pattern of the sandwich plate shown in Fig. 12 during thermal relaxation after stressing by overall temperature increase.

Research on the different ways of inducing deformation necessary for holographic nondestructive evaluation should be intensified to find better experimental conditions for interferometrical measurements, involving commercial aspects for a future more extensive use in the non-laboratory field of application.

REFERENCES

- 1 BUHMANN, K.P., STELLING, H.-A., and WINKLER, T.,
Kunststoffe Bd. 64 (1974), H. 12.
- 2 WINKLER, T. and SCHULZ, W., Preprint 13 th annual Meeting
of Arbeitsgemeinschaft Verstärkte Kunststoffe,
Freudenstadt, 1976.